

Hexacyanoferrate (II) Ascorbic Acid Reaction. Determination of Metaperiodate in Presence of Iodate

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The simple and accurate ascorbinometric determination of hexacyanoferrate (III) and the favourable redox potential of the hexacyanoferrate-ferrite (III)-(II) system has been utilised for the determination of several oxidising and reducing ions¹⁻². For the determination of reductants, excess of hexacyanoferrate (III) is used and the residual oxidant is titrated against ascorbic acid. In the case of oxidants, an excess of hexacyanoferrite (II) is added and the hexacyanoferrate (III) ions formed in the reaction are titrated with ascorbic acid. In the present communication a method based on this principle has been utilized for the determination of metaperiodate. Iodate does not interfere in this determination.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade (B.D.H., Analar or Merck, G.R.).

Suitable volumes of the solutions of potassium metaperiodate and potassium iodate were pipetted in a titration flask containing boric acid (0.5 g.) and excess of potassium hexacyanoferrite (II). After 1-2 minutes, 1 g. sodium bicarbonate and 1 ml. of 0.1% 2:4 dichlorophenol indophenol indicator were added and the reaction mixture was titrated against a standard solution of ascorbic acid to the disappearance of blue colour. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
Determination of metaperiodate in presence of iodate
(Solution contains 0.7188 g. KIO_4 /250 ml; and 0.8920 g. KIO_3 /250 ml)

Vol. taken (ml.)		KIO ₄ found (mg) by	
KIO ₄	KIO ₃	Iodometric method	Present method
10.0	30.0	28.7	28.7
15.0	25.0	43.1	43.1
20.0	20.0	57.5	57.4
25.0	15.0	71.9	71.9
30.0	10.0	86.2	86.3

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DISCUSSION

Potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) reacts with metaperiodate³, in presence of boric acid, in accordance with the equation :

Hexacyanoferrate (III) formed in the reaction has been estimated with ascorbic acid, in the presence of sodium bicarbonate, which corresponds to the amount of metaperiodate present in the solution. Iodate does not interfere in the determination of metaperiodate in this method since the latter is reduced to iodate state only. The end point is very sharp. Results have been compared with iodometric method⁴.

The authors express their thanks to the authorities of Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra for providing research facilities and to Dr. H. L. Bhatnagar, Professor of Chemistry for his keen interest and encouragement during the investigations.

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Received July 20, 1970

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